

Investigating the Impact of Channel Metrics in 5G NSA and SA on Video Streaming QoE

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Abstract—Evaluating the Quality of Experience (QoE) for over-the-top (OTT) video streaming is crucial due to increasing video traffic demands for delivering satisfactory user experiences. This work presents and evaluates a rich dataset capturing real-world 5G network performance and its impact on YouTube video streaming QoE. We utilized two US-based 5G networks to stream 2D YouTube videos and monitor cellular Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) at 1-second granularity. These KPIs include Channel Level Metrics (CLMs), such as RSRP, RSRQ, and SNR, and objective QoE metrics for various scenarios, including indoor and outdoor environments with different mobility conditions. We correlate CLMs KPIs in 5G Standalone (SA) and Non-Standalone (NSA) deployments with YouTube’s objective QoE. Our study shows performance differences where 5G SA encounters more streaming stalls during outdoor mobility than NSA, while SA supports higher resolutions in static indoor settings.

I. INTRODUCTION

Video streaming has emerged as a dominant force in internet traffic across fixed and mobile networks. Over-the-top (OTT) video platforms, such as YouTube, have become the leading sources of bandwidth consumption across these networks [1], [2]. Consequently, mobile networks are stressed due to the growing dependence on smartphones and other mobile devices for streaming high-definition content, including 4K/8K videos and immersive content.

To address these challenges, 5G and beyond technologies, particularly the New Radio (NR) technology, have been designed to offer enhanced capabilities such as ultra-low latency, high-speed data transfer, and massive device connectivity. 5G, with both Standalone (SA) and Non-Standalone (NSA) deployments, promises to significantly improve video streaming experiences by providing better Quality of Experience (QoE). However, under varying network conditions and mobility scenarios, deploying 5G networks and integrating them with existing 4G/LTE networks remains a complex endeavor [3].

To understand the impact of 5G network conditions, precisely the radio interface, on video streaming performance, it is essential to consider underlying Channel Level Metrics (CLMs) such as Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP), Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ), and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). These metrics provide valuable insights into network performance and can be key in predicting and mitigating QoE degradation. Analyzing

these CLMs alongside video QoE indicators, including stall, quality shifts, and resolutions, we can thoroughly understand how 5G deployment (e.g., SA or NSA) influences video playback under varying network conditions and user mobility.

In this work, we present the influence of CLMs on YouTube’s video objective QoE in 5G across different scenarios. The study includes streaming 4K YouTube 2D videos in both indoor and outdoor environments under varying mobility conditions for two US operators, anonymized as Operator-X and Operator-Y. As detailed in our previous work [3], the video preferences include various categories, including Sports, Animation, Movies, and Nature. Our main contributions can be summarized as follows:

- We collect CLMs in the wild from two operators along with YouTube objective QoE in a 5G SA and NSA deployments at one-second granularity.¹
- To the best of our knowledge, this work is the first publicly available dataset that contains CLMs and YouTube QoE logs in the wild with extreme mobility of 65-70 miles per hour (mph) for the research community.
- Our study shows distinct performance characteristics: in outdoor mobility scenarios, 5G SA exhibits more streaming stalls than NSA, while in static indoor scenarios, SA supports higher resolutions, achieving 4K resolution approximately 83% of the time.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents background and related work. In Section III, we introduce our methodology and dataset collection approach. Section IV provides results and discussions on CLMs and their effect on QoE followed by the conclusion in Section V.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Background. Mobile network operators have adopted two primary architectures in deploying 5G networks: NSA and SA. NSA leverages the existing 4G core network, while SA relies on a dedicated 5G core network. Both architectures require the deployment of a 5G NR Radio Access Network (RAN) composed of a set of Next Generation Node Bs (gNBs), i.e., the 5G equivalent of 4G Evolved Node Bs (eNBs) [3], [4]. For operators, efficient Radio Resource Management (RRM) ensures optimal network performance and user experience. Typically, RSRP, RSRQ, and SNR are

¹<https://github.com/razaulmustafa852/savsnsa5g>

key metrics for evaluating and managing signal strength and quality. RSRP measures the power of the primary signal received from the base station, while RSRQ evaluates the overall quality of the received signals. In contrast, SNR quantifies the signal power ratio to noise power. These well-known metrics are defined in four categories to classify the signal strengths: (i) Excellent, (ii) Good, (iii) Mid-cell, and (iv) Cell-edge [5]. Table I explains signal strengths categories and their corresponding ranges. Another crucial aspect for operators is ensuring seamless mobility, achieved through effective Handover (HO) mechanisms. HO is defined as transferring a device connection from one cell to another during mobility or cell reselection based on signal strength and quality. HO occurs when a user device’s current cell’s signal quality falls below a certain threshold or when the signal quality is poor. Operators implement various HO types, including (i) Intra-RAT, when a device moves from one 5G/4G base station to another 5G/4G base station; (ii) Inter-RAT, such handover occurs between different Radio Access Technology (RAT) networks, i.e., typically between different technologies; 4G to 5G.

Related Work. Mustafa et al. [3] conducted an extensive six-month study collecting channel and QoE logs in diverse scenarios. They proposed machine learning classifiers to predict video stalling events using CLMs. Their dataset includes various use cases, such as (i) Mobility, (ii) Pedestrian, (iii) Bus/Railway Terminals, and (iv) Static Outdoor. In contrast, this work extends these efforts by addressing extreme mobility scenarios, including dataset collection at speeds up to 65-70 mph. Additionally, we collect datasets in SA 5G deployments and utilize two major US mobile operators for data collection, which offers reproducibility to utilize the dataset for the research community to leverage in emulation environments [6]. In another work, Raca et al. [7] presented a dataset collected under two conditions: (i) Static and (ii) Car for two Irish mobile operators. Their work primarily focused on video streaming and file downloads during the data collection campaign. However, their dataset lacks detailed QoE metrics for popular video streaming platforms like Netflix and Amazon Prime. In contrast, our dataset offers a more comprehensive analysis by providing YouTube QoE Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) at a per-second granularity and diverse mobility use cases. In work [8], authors provided comprehensive bandwidth datasets on both 3G and 4G networks under vehicular driving conditions, which lack the current mode of 5G communication. In the context of extreme mobility, authors in [9] analyzed the impacts of high-speed mobility and HO on performance metrics, including RTT, packet loss, and network disconnection. However, in our work, we take extreme mobility into account to investigate the effect of channel metrics on YouTube’s QoE. Similarly, in another work [10], authors considered high-speed railways to explore mobile data network performance. They found that TCP throughput and RTT are worse than stationary use cases due to frequent HOs. Compared to all the works men-

TABLE I: Understanding Signal Strengths [5].

Category	RSRP (dBm)	RSRQ (db)	SNR (db)
Excellent	≥ -80	≥ -10	≥ 20
Good	$-80 : -90$	$-10 : -15$	$13 : 20$
Mid-cell	$-90 : 100$	$-15 : -20$	$0 : 13$
Cell-edge	≤ -100	< -20	≤ 0

tioned above, our dataset considers YouTube video streaming sessions and collected channel metrics with 1-second granularity. We consider static/stationary, low-, moderate- and extreme mobility to cover all the use cases under 5G SA and NSA deployment. Since we provide QoE KPIs for the popular video streaming platform YouTube alongside corresponding channel metrics. This enables researchers to analyze the relationship between channel conditions and QoE degradation of video streaming and create opportunities such as leveraging machine learning techniques for performance optimization.

III. METHODOLOGY

The two main software components used in our data collection campaign are (i) YouTube Iframe API, which provides YouTube QoE logs and (ii) G-NetTrack Pro, a 5G/4G/3G/2G network monitoring and drive test application tool for Android devices (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1: Dataset Collection Overview.

YouTube Iframe API. It allows YouTube players to be embedded in a web application by controlling the player’s functionality using JavaScript. The API uses event-based programming to provide KPIs for the videos in play. We implemented the Iframe API into a custom web application that requests a use case name (indoor, mobility, extreme mobility, etc.) and the video to play. After providing this information, the web application invokes the YouTube Iframe API to play the video. Meanwhile, we created a custom Ajax-based script to save player information in the database after every second², such as video bytes downloaded in the buffer and current resolutions. Similarly, we save player events in the database such as (0 – Ended, 1 – Playing, 2 – Paused, 3 – Stall, 5 – Cued, -1 – Unstarted).

G-NetTrack Pro. We used G-NetTrack Pro to collect channel metrics. It provides 5G/4G/3G/2G serving and neighboring cell information and saves it in log files (text and KML format). We set a 1-second granularity for logs in the setting.

²github.com/razaulmustafa852/savsnsa5g/blob/main/javascript-code.php

TABLE II: CLMs and YouTube Player Logs and Events for Use Case – Indoor, Technology – 5G NSA Operator-X.

Channel Metrics					Player Logs				Player Events		
Time	RSRP	RSRQ	SNR	DL_bitrate	Time	Quality	VBD	LP	Time	Quality	Event
22:48:16	-111	-15	-3.0	1463	22:48:16	medium	0.17	17	-	-	-
22:48:17	-111	-15	-3.0	1406	22:48:17	medium	0.17	17	22:48:17	hd2160	buffering
22:48:18	-109	-14	0	1587	22:48:18	hd2160	0.0	0	-	-	-
22:48:19	-109	-14	0	1532	22:48:19	hd2160	0.0	0	-	-	-
22:48:20	-113	-17	-5	1555	22:48:20	hd2160	0.0	0	-	-	-

We provide an example of logs that we saved in the database in Table II. The video played during the video streaming session has video ID (VMs0yEVC00A), and the total length is 4-min 30-sec. The video has qualities (240p, 360p, 480p, 720p, 1080p, 1440p, 2160p) and available on YouTube as named “2 Weeks In Italy : A Cinematic Travel Film”. During the video streaming session, we forced the player to play in 4K by invoking event *setPlaybackQuality(hd2160)*. However, forcing doesn’t always run the streaming session in hd2160; depending on network conditions, the player adapts to other resolutions. The logs shown in Table II have three sections: (i) Channel Metrics, (ii) QoE logs of the YouTube Player, and (iii) Player Events. We showed the 5-second logs starting from the time (22:48:16). The channel metrics RSRP and RSRQ for this 5-sec chunk remain (-113) to (-109), and (-17) to (-14) and SNR values remain in (-3) and (-5). This chunk’s throughput or Download Bitrate (DL_bitrate) starts at 1463 kbps and reaches 1555 kbps. The quality jumps from medium to hd2160, and the loaded percentage or Video Bytes Downloaded (VBD) in the buffer changes from 17 to 0 in 5-sec; therefore, experiencing buffering at (22:48:17).

Data Collection Approach. For three months of the campaign, we opted for two well-known Operators (Operator-X and Operator-Y) in the US. We collected the dataset in the downtown area, surrounded by huge buildings. We collected Static (indoor) and Low mobility (outdoor) datasets at the downtown hub. However, we run campaigns 10-15 miles and 200-300 miles from downtown for moderate- and extreme mobility (outdoor), respectively. We use public buses for moderate mobility and personal cars for extreme mobility. The device used during the dataset collection was *Samsung A32 5G*, and we used an unlimited data package for both operators. The web application was built using *PHP, MySQL, and JavaScript/Ajax*. Figure 1 shows the block diagram designed for the study. The web application requests the name of the use case, selects a video from a dropdown, and saves QoE logs to MySQL, while G-NetTrack Pro runs in the background to collect channel logs every second.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Channel Logs - (Indoor, Low, Moderate and Extreme Mobility) and Their Impact on QoE

This section presents 25%, 50%, and 50% percentile of four use cases: Indoor and Low-, Moderate-, and Extreme mobility in Table III. During the Indoor use case, the 25-, 50-, and 75-percentiles for RSRP remain in a very poor range (see Table III), leading to lower data rates and frequent quality

shifts and buffering events (see Table IV). We observe similar patterns for RSRQ and SNR, which can be categorized into the Fair and Poor range. Next, in Low mobility, RSRP maintains a stable connection and provides good network performance. However, RSRQ and SNR provide behavior similar to indoor settings. The moderate use case also remains in a stable connection. Therefore, RSRP, RSRQ, and SNR strength remain in the fair-to-good range during the video streaming session, with an increasing trend suggesting a generally improving signal. Lastly, we have a use case for extreme mobility, where RSRP values (-82 dBm at the 75th percentile) indicate strong and reliable signals. We observe similar patterns for RSRQ and SNR. Through these percentile scores of randomly selected use cases, we cannot definitively determine the overall impact of channel metrics on the QoE of YouTube streaming sessions. However, we observe that RSRP plays a more significant role in QoE than the other two metrics. We further investigate the impact in the following subsections to conclude our findings.

B. (SA vs. NSA) Channel Metrics and Their Impact on QoE

We show the comparison of all the use cases in Figure 2 and Table V. We observe a distinct difference between Low Mobility (Pedestrian) and Moderate Mobility (Bus). For instance, in Figure 2 (a), RSRQ for the use case Low Mobility, 80% of the time remains in a range between (-12 – -15), whereas in the case of Moderate Mobility, the range is (-5 – -9). In contrast, for Indoor, the range is (-12 – -13). While comparing NSA vs. SA channel metrics, we observe similar patterns for Indoor NSA vs. Indoor SA. However, Low Mobility SA exhibits better values than Low Mobility NSA, while Moderate Mobility NSA outperforms Moderate Mobility SA. As referenced in Table I, RSRQ (NSA) shows better results than SA. Although SA signals remain in a good range, SA suffers from quality shifts (see Table V).

Next, RSRP (NSA) in Figure 2 (b) for Low- and Moderate Mobility shows a better score compared to Indoor. However, while comparing NSA vs. SA, we observed similar patterns for all use cases, i.e., Indoor, Low- and Moderate Mobility. Similarly, SNR (NSA) for Moderate Mobility in Figure 2 (c) is again better than Low Mobility (NSA). At the same time, SA metrics follow similar patterns to Indoor, Low- and Moderate Mobility.

Though in Figure 2, we observe Low- and Moderate Mobility have some significant change in their values, but their impact on QoE is quite remarkable (see Table V). During the Indoor NSA use case, we observe frequent

TABLE III: 25%, 50%, 75% of Randomly Selected Use Cases from NSA Technology and Operator-X.

	Indoor			Low			Moderate			Extreme		
Percentile	25%	50%	75%	25%	50%	75%	25%	50%	75%	25%	50%	75%
RSRP	-112.00	-110.00	-104.00	-95.00	-90.00	-86.00	-109.00	-102.00	-96.00	-94.00	-88.00	-82.00
RSRQ	-14.00	-13.00	-12.00	-14.00	-13.00	-12.00	-12.00	-11.00	-11.00	-11.00	-11.00	-11.00
SNR	0.00	2.00	3.00	0.00	2.00	5.00	3.00	9.00	15.00	8.00	13.00	17.00
Bitrate	5.00	1426.00	1539.25	3.00	4.00	63.75	3.00	4.50	303.25	4.00	5.00	1997.00

Fig. 2: Indoor, Low Mobility, Moderate Mobility Channel Metrics (RSRQ, RSRP, SNR) – (Operator-X) – NSA vs SA.

TABLE IV: QoE Events of the Video Streaming Session.

Quality	Time	Event
medium	22:47:55	Playing
hd2160	22:48:17	Buffering
small	22:49:49	Playing
small	22:50:04	Buffering
small	22:50:04	Playing
hd2160	22:52:07	Buffering
medium	22:53:20	Playing
large	22:54:12	Ended

TABLE V: Impact of NSA and SA 5G Technologies on QoE Metrics – Resolutions.

Quality	Indoor		Low Mobility		Moderate Mobility	
	NSA	SA	NSA	SA	NSA	SA
hd2160	28.49	83.30	100.00	54.70	100.00	17.18
hd1440	5.43					1.17
hd1080	7.26			1.70		28.84
hd720	7.05					4.93
large	39.64	14.03		31.45		35.90
medium	6.95	2.65		1.36		11.84
small	5.16			10.76		0.10

quality fluctuations. For example, hd2160 quality accounts for 28.49% of the total experiment, while hd1440 remains at just 5.43%, hd1080 at 7.26%, and hd720 at 7.05%. Additionally, large quality constitutes 39.64%, medium 6.95%, and small quality remains at 5.16%. Whereas, in SA deployment, hd2160 quality accounts for 83.30% followed by large and medium just for 14.03% and 2.65%, respectively.

In contrast, we observe distinct patterns for outdoor Low- and Moderate Mobility, where SA deployment experienced more quality shifts than NSA deployment. The reason could be the frequent handover as seen in Table VI. For Low Mobility, i.e., Pedestrian in NSA, the dominant resolution remains hd2160 for all the experiments done in the wild. However,

TABLE VI: Handover for Low- and Moderate Mobility.

Handover Events	Low		Moderate	
	NSA	SA	NSA	SA
HANDOVER DATA 5G5G	16	15	6	74
HANDOVER DATA 4G4G	3	3	1	3
CELL RESELECTION 5G5G	1	2	-	7
IRAT HANDOVER DATA 5G4G	1	6	3	11
IRAT HANDOVER DATA 4G5G	-	6	2	13

we observe frequent resolution changes in the SA deployment of 5G. For instance, hd2160 accounts for 54.70%, hd1080 at 1.70%, and the second dominant resolution is *large*, which constitutes 31.45% followed by medium and small with a percentage of 1.36% and 10.76% respectively. We observe similar patterns in Moderate Mobility, i.e., experiments done in public transport in the downtown area. Similar to Low Mobility, SA deployment experiences frequent quality shifts with dominant resolution as *large* (35.90%) followed by second dominant hd1080 as 28.84%. Next, hd2160 accounts for 17.18%, hd1440 as 1.17%, hd720 as 4.93% and small as 0.10%.

Our observations from QoE and channel metrics are the following:

- Although the channel measurements for NSA and SA were similar, SA 5G deployment experiences frequent quality shifts.
- Indoor experiments were static as no mobility was involved. Thus, NSA experiences more quality shifts compared to SA 5G deployment.
- Quality shifts in SA deployment could be due to more frequent handovers, as user devices require a reasonable time to adjust to new base station signals, i.e., RSRP, RSRQ, and SNR.

Fig. 3: Indoor Channel Metrics (RSRQ, RSRP, SNR) – (Operator-X) vs.(Operator-Y) in NSA Mode.

C. Channel Metrics Operator-X vs. Operator-Y

This section compares two operators (Operator X and Y); see Figure 3. Two operators are entirely different in their channel metrics; for instance, in RSRQ and RSRP, Operator Y is way behind Operator X. 40% of the time, Operator-Y RSRQ values remain in the range (-14 – -17), whereas Operator-X is in the range (-12 – -14). Similarly, RSRP for Operator-Y remains in the range (> -150), and Operator-X in the range (> -100); thus, both stay at Cell-edge. Finally, SNR for Operator-X, 80% of the time, the range is (3-5), whereas, for Operator-Y, the range is (7-10); thus, both stay at Cell-edge. Please note: The indoor use case is the only comparison available in NSA technology for operators X and Y. Since we conducted most of our experiments in NSA deployments, we lack the data necessary to compare channel metrics for all other use cases.

TABLE VII: Buffering Events During the Streaming.

Indoor		Low Mob.		Moderate Mob.		Extreme Mob.	
NSA	SA	NSA	SA	NSA	SA	NSA	SA
56	11	3	15	2	13	17	-

D. Do Channel Metrics Impact QoE Degradation?

To address this question, we examine all stalling/buffering events during our dataset collection campaign. We focus on Low- and Moderate mobility SA deployment use cases to explore how channel metrics affect QoE, as the majority of stalling events occur during mobility. First, we noted the time of the stalling event in the YouTube QoE logs and then investigated 10 seconds before and after the channel metrics, i.e., RSRP, RSRQ, and SNR. The choice of 10 seconds is based on the fact that the player has enough time to decide, such as quality shift based on the interruptions [3]. The results are shown in Figures 4 and 5. In Figure 4, we observe similar patterns for RSRQ and SNR, while in RSRP, the distribution before 10-seconds is (-150 to -50), whereas after 10-seconds the distribution is (-100 to -80), therefore, a high score after 10 seconds influences the bitrate and improves the QoE. Similarly, in Figure 5, RSRQ and RSRP constitute better scores after 10 seconds, hence better QoE. Our observations from the experiments are the following:

TABLE VIII: Channel Metrics - Extreme Mobility (Oper.-Y).

Extreme Mobility					
Metrics	Mean	STD	25%	50%	75%
RSRP	-157.94	118.17	-121.00	-108.00	-100.00
RSRQ	-11.69	51.60	-18.00	-12.00	-11.00
SNR	9.46	8.24	3.0	9.00	16.00
Bitrate	743.76	1424.97	4.0	4.00	1187.75

TABLE IX: QoE Metrics During Extreme Mobility.

QoE Metrics						
hd2160	hd1080	hd720	Large	Medium	Small	Tiny
1.05	7.21	16.92	67.73	6.84	0.15	0.07

- Poor signal strength and quality indeed impact the QoE of YouTube, as we have seen from Figures 4 and 5.
- SA deployment experiences more stalling events than NSA in Low- and Moderate mobility. This is due to handover events (also mentioned before) during the streaming sessions (see Table VI).
- SA deployment provides a better QoE score than NSA in a static mode (Indoor), where we observe that the dominant resolution is hd2160, which accounts for 83.30% (see Table V).
- Based on Table V, VII and Figures 4, 5 we conclude that: (i) SA deployment offers a better experience in static mode due to lower handover and stalling events; (ii) Low- and Moderate mobility suffers from recurring handover events, causing frequent quality shifts and stalling.

E. Extreme Mobility at 65-70 mph.

In this section, we explain the extreme mobility use cases. We covered 300 miles and ran all the videos [3]. During these experiments, there were frequent shifts between 4G-LTE and NSA-5G. Therefore, we provide statistics of these experiments separately, and we also argue that the experiments are not comparable to other mobility use cases as we only have NSA technology.

We show the Mean, Standard Deviation (STD), 25%, 50% and 75% percentile of all the channel logs in Table VIII. The mean for RSRP, RSRQ and SNR remains -157.94, -11.69, and 9.46, respectively, whereas the bitrate (throughput)

Fig. 4: 10 Seconds Before and After the Stalling Event in Low Mobility SA 5G Deployment (Operator-X).

Fig. 5: 10 Seconds Before and After the Stalling Event in Moderate Mobility SA 5G Deployment (Operator-X).

through these all experiments is 743.76, with deviation as 1424.97 and (25, 50, 75)% percentile as (4, 4, 1187.75). From bitrate, we conclude that 75% is the third quartile or the 75th percentile, meaning 75% of the data is below 1187.75 kbps.

The QoE events during the extreme mobility are shown in Tables VII and IX. During the dataset campaign, we experience 17 stalling events and frequent changes in the technology, i.e., 4G to 5G and 5G to 4G. Moreover, hd2160, also known as 4K resolution (2160p), accounts for only 1.05% of the streaming sessions. Whereas the dominant resolution is, *large* with an overall percentage compared to others is 67.73%. Next, the dominant resolution is hd720, with a 16.92% overall share. All other resolutions during this campaign are mentioned in Table IX. Our observations are the following:

- Due to frequent changes in technology, i.e., 4G to 5G and vice-versa, it becomes highly challenging for YouTube to consistently stream videos in 4K quality.
- During extreme mobility, the player switches to different resolutions to avoid stalls instead of requesting the chunk with a high bitrate.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a dataset containing 5G network traces from two major US mobile operators and video streaming performance under different mobility scenarios. The dataset comprises channel-level metrics and objective QoE metrics of video streaming from the YouTube platform on the client side. The result analysis demonstrated how the different 5G deployments, NSA and SA, affected YouTube QoE per-

formance, considering key channel metrics such as RSRQ, RSRP, and SNR. It highlights the performance differences between the two deployments, with 5G SA exhibiting more streaming interruptions in mobility scenarios while supporting higher resolutions in static environments. These findings emphasize the importance of network conditions and mobility factors on user QoE in 5G networks.

This study has limitations that future research could address. First, using YouTube as the baseline for 2D video streaming analysis limits the generalizability to other platforms. Therefore, there is a scope to broaden this by including both 2D and omnidirectional videos on various platforms that would enhance understanding of 5G’s impact on video streaming. Second, anonymizing operators limits insights into the specifics of their infrastructure. Future studies could incorporate details on operators’ network setups (if permissible) to see how configurations affect QoE. Additionally, incorporating extreme conditions such as network congestion or high-density areas beyond the current mobility scenarios would provide a more comprehensive perspective on 5G performance and its effect on QoE. We are also interested in investigating how generative AI can interact with our dataset to produce new data.

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